

FDI in Retail Sector in India: A Critical Review

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Abstract

Foreign direct investment (FDI) plays an important role in India's growth dynamics. There are several examples of the benefits of FDI in India. FDI in the retail sector can expand markets by reducing transaction and transformation costs of business through adoption of advanced supply chain and benefit consumers, and suppliers (farmers). This also can result in net gains in employment at the aggregate level. Opposition to liberalizing FDI in this sector raises concerns about employment losses, unfair competition resulting in large-scale exit of incumbent domestic retailers and infant industry arguments to protect the organized domestic retail sector that is at a nascent stage. Based on international evidence, we suggest that allowing entry by large international retailers into the Indian market may help tackle inflation especially in food prices. Moreover, technical know-how from foreign firms, such as warehousing technologies and distribution systems can improve supply chain efficiency in India, in particular for agricultural produce. Better linkages between demand and supply have the potential to improve the price signals that farmers receive and also serve to enhance agricultural and other exports. In the past few decades large retailers have experienced substantial growth around the world. Evidence suggests while the impact of entry by large retail chains on employment and incumbent mom-and-pop stores is mixed, there can be substantial benefits to consumers in the form of lower prices and lowered food price inflation in particular. Similarly, by employing improved distribution and warehousing technologies, large retail chains are in a position to provide better price signals to farmers and to serve as a platform for enhanced exports.

Keywords: Foreign Direct Investment, Liberalization, Retail, India.Growth

Introduction

Indian retail sector is highly fragmented as compared to the developed as well as the other developing countries. This shows a great potential for the organized retail industry to prosper in India, as the market for the final consumption in India is very large. Retail trade is largely in the hands of private independent owners and distributor's structure for fast moving consumer goods consisting of multiple layers such as carrying and forwarding agents, distributors, stockiest, wholesalers and retailers. Thus, the growth potential for the organized retailer is enormous. In the next 2-3 years, India will finally see operations of a number of very serious international players- net withstanding the current restrictions on FDI in retail. The Indian retail sector is ready to take on challenges from global retail players such as Wal-mart and Carrefour because unlike them, they have a better understanding of the Indian consumer's psyche. Ultimately, a successful retailer is one who understands his customer. The Indian customer is looking for an emotional connection, a sense of belonging. Hence, to be successful any retail outlet has to be localized. The customer should feel that it is a part of his culture, his perceived values, and does not try to impose alien values or concepts on him. Indian customer is not keen to buy something just because it is sold by an international company.

FDI Scenario in India

In 1991, the Indian government introduced the economic policy to attract foreign investments and since then, it has amended the policy from time to time in various sectors to allow higher levels of

foreign participation. The government policy in retail sector allows 100% foreign investment in wholesale cash-and-carry and single-brand retailing but prohibits investments in retail trading. In 1997, the government imposed restrictions on FDI in retail sector but in 2006, these were lifted and opened in single-brand retailing and in cash-and-carry formats. The cash-and-carry business is the easiest mode of entry for foreign retailers into India. Many global players like Metro and Shoprite have already entered the market. Wal-mart has forged an alliance with Bharti for a cash-and-carry business, and Bharti is concentrating on front-end retail. Similarly, Tesco has entered India through an alliance with Trent (Tata Group). Apart from investing in the cash-and-carry business, Trent will also support the back-end activities of Trent Ltd. Many foreign brands have also entered India either through JVs with leading Indian retailers or through exclusive franchisees to set up shop in India. Louis Vuitton, Marks & Spencer Plc, GAS, Armani are some such operators who have entered India through JVs. McDonald's, KFC, Domino's are the retailers who have taken the franchise route.

Slowly the government is opening up to the idea of permitting FDI in the Indian retail sector; consequently there is greater momentum in the sector. Last year, owing to the global meltdown, investments dropped in all sectors. The government has therefore changed the guidelines for foreign investments to boost investments in the current year. This move is certainly likely to improve the investment climate in the Indian retail space. Investments in the retail sector have improved since

FDI has been allowed in single-brand and cash-and-carry formats. According to the Technopak estimates, investments in the organised retail will touch US\$ 35 billion in the next five years or so. Investments allow organised players in retail to expand at a very high rate. All key retailers in India have expansion plans over the next 3-4 years; for instance, Pantaloon has an ambitious expansion plan to take its retail space up to 30 million square feet by 2011. Likewise, Vishal Retail is expected to take its total store count to 500 with an estimated retail space of around 10 million square feet by 2011.

Present Scenario

Retailing in India is witness to the boom in terms of modern retailing formats, shopping malls etc. the future of retailing for any product across the country will definitely be in malls where the consumer can get variety, quality and ambience. However, in spite of this continuous debate to be or not to be, recently Government has allowed up to 51 percent FDI in single brand retailing by foreign companies like Reebok and Louis Vuiton. As of now, single brand retailers operate through the franchisee route and there is a strong view that FDI in this segment would not displace jobs or impact the local industry but help create employment. Even today the government is undecided about the level FDI in retail, but a number of foreign players, including the Wal-mart stores, Inc., have announced their intention to enter India in a big way. At present Wal-mart is operating through its subsidiary in Bangalore, which was functioning as a liaison office till last year. Now it is in the process of setting up offices in New Delhi and Mumbai.

Retailing In the 21st Century

In today's dynamic and shaky business world, the retail industry is constantly upgrading itself. With an endless array of customer choices, fierce competitors, pervasive use of the internet, and a complex global economy, retailers need to focus on finding ways to sustain and grow their businesses. Traditional growth models that focused on rolling out more stores and adding more product lines, no longer enjoy the return on investment they once did. Successful retailers are those who are able to adapt and change to the environment and develop new ways of serving customers, respecting the dynamics of current trends and adapting accordingly.

The retail industry in India is hailed as a sunrise sector, and is estimated to double in value from US\$ 330 billion in 2007 to \$640 billion by 2015. In fact, India has topped AT Kearney's annual Global Retail Development Index (GRDI) for the third year in a row as the most attractive market for retail investment.

The bad news is, despite the fact that India has one of the largest number of retail outlets in the World, organized retail accounts for only 4% of the total

market. This makes it especially difficult to apply sophisticated merchandising and sales tools, enhance consumer interaction and also, make very accurate analysis. That said, analysts believe the sector is likely to show significant growth of over 9 % p.a over the next 10 years and also see rapid development in organized retail formats, with the proportion likely to reach a more respectable 25% by 2018.

Indian retail food industry has revolutionized shopping experience of Indian customers. Growing at the rate of 30%, the Indian food retail is going to be and no doubt is the major driving force for the retail industry. Food accounts for the largest share of consumer spending. Food and food products account for about 50% of the value of final private consumption. This share is significantly higher compared to developed economies, where food and food products account for about 20% of consumer spending. Ireena Vittal, principal, McKinsey & Co in Food Forum 2008, said, "At US\$ 175 billion today the food industry is likely to grow to US\$ 400 billion by 2025. The percentage of income spent in households will drive growth in the food market. Indian consumers are happy with store goods than branded goods and are very conservative on packaged goods. There are 10 million street vendors in India, of which 6 million only sell food. Currently, the retail food sector is US\$ 70 billion and is expected to rise to US\$ 150 billion by 2025. Food has the largest consumption in the Indian economy and will remain the single largest category." Modern state of the food retailing is not a demand led but the supply led one. Major spending on food and increasing usage of out of home food consumption represent a significant opportunity for food retailers and food service companies. Speaking in Food Forum India 2008, on the government's role in the food retailing development, Dave said, "The retail stores need to empower its stakeholders and deliver what the consumer wants. The vision for 2020 should be appropriate extension network, implementation of appropriate practice at farmers' level and infrastructure in the country."

Retail In India - The Future

According to a study the size of the Indian Retail market is currently estimated at Rs.704 crores, which accounts for a meager 3% of the total retail market. As the market becomes more and more organized the Indian retail industry will gain greater worth. The Retail sector in the small towns and cities will increase by 50% to 60% pertaining to easy and inexpensive availability of land and demand among consumers. Growth in India Real estate sector is also complementing the Retail sector and thus it becomes a strong feature for the future trend. Over a period of next 4 years there will be a

retail space demand of 40 million sq. ft. However with growing real estate sector space constraint will not be there to meet this demand. The growth in the retail sector is also caused by the development of retail specific properties like malls and multiplexes. According to a report, from the year 2003 to 2008 the retail sales are growing at a rate of 8.3% per annum. With this the organized retail which currently has only 3% of the total market share will acquire 15%-20% of the market share by the year 2010.

Factors that are playing a role in fuelling the bright future of the Indian Retail are as follows:

1. The income of an average Indian is increasing and thus there is a proportional increase in the purchasing power.
2. The infrastructure is improving greatly in all regions is benefiting the market.

3. Indian economy and its policies are also becoming more and more liberal making way for a wide range of companies to enter Indian market.
4. Indian population has learnt to become a good consumer and all national and international brands are benefiting with this new awareness.
5. Another great factor is the internet revolution, which is allowing foreign brands to understand Indian consumers and influence them before entering the market. Due to the reach of media in the remotest of the markets, consumers are now aware of the global products and it helps brands to build themselves faster in a new region
6. Indian Retail Landscape

Table No.1 Raising income and increase consumerism are fueling retail growth.

SI NO	YEAR	\$ billion retail growth
1	1998	201
2	2000	204
3	2002	238
4	2004	278
5	2006*	321
6	2008*	368
7	2010*	421

Sources: Retail in India-A CII-AT Kearney report

According to NCEAR forecasts, the number of 'rich' households (the target market for modern retail stores) is expected to more than double from 57 million in 2002 to 107 million by 2010. The proportion of India's population that is less than 25 years of age stands at more than 50 percent currently while more than 80 percent of the population is below the age of 45 years. This 'young population' segment is driving the changes in consumption habits and spending patterns. An increasing proportion of the young population is joining the work force, and adding to overall spending, which should bode well for the growth of modern retail formats in India. Growing urbanization (malls are likely to be concentrated in urban areas) is also fuelling modern retail format growth. It is expected that India's urban population will grow from 21 percent of the overall population in 2000 to 32 percent by 2010.

Change accelerators

The following factors will be significant in driving growth in the retail sector:

Consumer factors

1. Increase in income
2. Working women
3. Changes in lifestyle demand for 'global' trend

Supply side factors

1. Growing importance of retailing in political and economic agenda.

2. Real estate reforms to be undertaken in the next 24 months.
3. Major restructuring of the manufacturing sector easing product supply constraints for efficient retailing.
4. Reduction in import duties- offering more global sourcing options.

Opportunities in Retail Sector:

These are giving an opportunity to various other retail formats:

A. Neighbourhood Stores

In India about 90% of food purchases are made within a distance of 1.5 km from the customer's home. This means that an organised retailer would need to have a 'neighbourhood store' close to customers in order to capture the share of wallet that is spent on food. These stores would cater to the consumer's daily and weekly needs. The outlets closest to a neighbourhood store in India are 'Safal' outlets operated by Mother Dairy in Delhi, Margin Free in Kerala and Subhiksha.

B. Supermarkets

This format caters to the consumers' need for choice and variety. These needs translate into 'more width' and 'more depth' in each category. These stores cater to the consumers in a catchment area with a radius of 3 to 4 km and therefore need to be destination stores. A supermarket can cater to the consumers' weekly, monthly and occasional needs. Examples of

supermarkets already in India are Food World, Trinetra and Nilgiri's.

C. Hypermarkets

Hypermarkets are essentially destination stores catering to the consumers' bulk shopping needs in both food and non-food categories. The key added values for the customer are 'choice' and 'value for money' because products are sold at a discounted price. The hypermarkets model of food retailing is new to India. Spencers (RPG), Big Bazaar (Pantaloons), Star India Bazaar.

D. Cash & Carry (C & C) Stores

These stores sell their products to their members only. The members are typically retailers and institutions. The key added value is a wide range of products under one roof, available at wholesale prices. Metro has started the first C & C store in India in Bangalore. The typical area of a C & C store is 70,000 to 100,000 sq. ft. and both food and non-food products are stocked.

Recommendations:

1. The retail sector in India is severely constrained **by limited availability of bank finance**. The Government and RBI need to evolve suitable lending policies that will enable retailers in the organised and unorganised sectors to expand and improve efficiencies. Policies that encourage unorganised sector retailers to migrate to the organised sector by investing in space and equipment should be encouraged.
2. A **National Commission** must be established to study the problems of the retail sector and to evolve policies that will enable it to cope with FDI – as and when it comes.
3. The government must actively encourage setting up of **co-operative stores** to procure and stock their consumer goods and commodities from small producers. This will address the dual problem of limited promotion and marketing ability, as well as market penetration for the retailer. The government can also facilitate the setting up of warehousing units and cold chains, thereby lowering the capital costs for the small retailers.
4. Set up an **Agricultural Perishable Produce Commission (APPC)**, to ensure that procurement prices for perishable commodities are fair to farmers and that they are not distorted with relation to market prices.
5. Creation of **infrastructure** for retailing at mandis, community welfare centers, government and private colonies with a thrust on easier logistics and hygiene will enable greater employment and higher hygiene consciousness, and faster turnaround of transport and higher rollover of produce.

Conclusion

The retail sector has played a phenomenal role throughout the world in increasing productivity of consumer goods and services. It is also the second largest industry in US in terms of numbers of employees and establishments. There is no denying the fact that most of the developed economies are very much relying on their retail sector as a locomotive of growth. The Retail Industry in India has come forth as one of the most dynamic and fast paced industries with several players entering the market. But all of them have not yet tasted success because of the heavy initial investments that are required to break even with other companies and compete with them. The India Retail Industry is gradually inching its way towards becoming the next boom industry. Favorable government policies and continued growth will mean that the future belongs to the most aggressive players. The future is already planned for few investments in the coming 2-3 years. Though the retailers will have to face increasingly demanding customers and intensely competitive rivals, more investments will keep flowing in and the share of organized food sector will grow rapidly.

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